

Effect of intensive light trapping^a on the rice brown planthopper during an outbreak in Sg. Burong, Tanjung Karang, Malaysia.

Planthopper count	Planthoppers/hill (no.)		
	Macropterous adults	Brachypterous adults	Nymphs
Before light trapping ^b	397	367	174
After light trapping	156	12	492

^aTwenty pressure lamp traps were placed around the infested field between 1830 and 2300 hours.

^bAug. 2, 1977.

Population counts of the BPH over 140 randomly selected hills covering 14 sample points showed that the BPH population declined drastically soon after the light trapping (see figure). The

Change in brown planthopper population in localities with intensive light trapping (Sg. Leman) and without light traps (Sawah Sempadan and Sg. Burong). Arrow and number above indicate, respectively, the night and number of light traps in operation.

total catches for the three successive nights were 2.88, 3.42, and 4.29 million BPH, respectively. The fact that only the macropterous adults were generally caught (see table) accounted for the residual population observed in the figure.

For comparison, the populations of BPH were measured for the same periods at two other localities, Sawah Sempadan and Sg. Burong, where light trapping was not used. In these areas, the population was not significantly reduced (see figure).

The findings show that intensive light trapping could rapidly remove large BPH populations in an outbreak. Theoretically, one light trap/0.4 ha (1 trap/acre) might remove as many as 141 BPH/hill, or even more if the efficiency of the traps could be increased. The lowering of a BPH population before insecticide control may prove critical, as chemicals generally are not effective enough to prevent hopperburn during outbreaks.

Although intensive light trapping might play an important role, its use as the sole means of control still requires further investigation. Success seems possible only if the BPH population is composed mostly of the macropterous adults.

Outbreak of *Heteronychus oryzae* in rice seedlings near Rokupr, Sierra Leone

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During early June 1977, an outbreak of *Heteronychus oryzae* occurred at Magbolontor, near a mangrove swamp where extensive rice experimental trials are conducted by the Rice Research Station, Rokupr.

All the experimental fields and nurseries at Magbolontor had been direct-seeded at about the end of May. At about the two-leaf stage, glossy dark-brown beetles (*Heteronychus oryzae*) began to attack the rice seedlings.

Damage to rice seedlings by *Heteronychus oryzae* at Magbolontor, Sierra Leone, 8 June 1977.

Variety	Seedling infestation (%)
2526	1.7
Huallaga	4.2
052/37	4.5
Ngovie	5.5
Bakutu	6.3
Parmatis	8.0
Gissi 27	8.1
Andy 301	9.2
ROK 4	12.8
Adny 4	29.9
Sokopent	33.8
Babadin	45.5
Gbinteh	49.5
Pa Panel	51.0
M-207	52.0
ROK 3	72.6 ^a
BD 2	87.5
Mahsuri	94.5

^aSample unit was 1 sq m. Twenty sample units were taken in 1.4-ha seed multiplication fields, and two sample units were recorded from each plot of the other varieties for varietal observation experiments.

found, mostly at the base of the plant. Surprisingly, not a single bug was found in the dry nurseries. Farmers were advised to spray dieldrin, gamma BHC, methyl parathion, malathion, or dichlorvos. Less expensive chemicals such as DDT or BHC, either as dust or spray, have been found equally effective.

Outbreak of Malayan black rice bug in Nellore district

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A sudden outbreak of Malayan black rice bug *Scotinophara coarcata* was noted in the last week of May 1977 in Nellore district, Andhra Pradesh. The bug had earlier been reported to damage rice crops

in other parts of India. In 150 ha of rabi paddy, infestation was severe in CO 29 and IET 2508 varieties at the time of flowering. Yield losses of from 60 to 85% were recorded. The bugs also seriously damaged almost 100 ha of IET 2508 in the transplanted early kharif crop. They seemed to prefer young seedlings; in some places, nurseries of CO 29 and IET 2508 were almost totally destroyed. Irrigation water was standing in the affected plots although the weather was mostly dry. In heavily infested plots, about 200 bugs/hill were

The insects damaged the stem below the ground by nibbling, leaving the attacked parts fibrous. The leaves withered and turned brown. The beetles then moved below the soil surface, leaving behind a raised track and damaging other seedlings.

The extent of damage varied among the varieties (see table). Many of the experimental fields had to be resown.

Dieldrex 20 and Agroicide 26 DP applied at 0.085 and 0.25%, respectively, suppressed the infestation.

Effects of root-dip pesticide treatments on root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne graminicola*

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Surveillance profile for pest management

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A surveillance profile for pest management consists of a series of circles and squares that are connected to surveillance dates ($T_1, T_2 - - T_n$). The circle indicates "action needed," and the square, "action not needed" (see figure).

The use of this simple method begins shortly after planting the crop. To make decisions on "action needed" and "action not needed," the economic threshold level for the pest should first be known. Sampling stations or plots are then staked out at representative parts of the field. Surveillance is carried out at each station

by examining a specified number of randomly selected plants. If the pest population on the plant exceeds or approaches the established threshold level on a surveillance date, a circle is checked. If it is below the threshold level, a square is checked. This procedure is carried out for each surveillance date and for each plot throughout the surveillance period.

The surveillance profile gives growers and pest management specialists a visual running account of the pest severity on a crop. The effects of insecticide treatments, cultural practices, and, in certain instances, weather changes can be evaluated. A detailed description of the surveillance profile will be published in a forthcoming issue of the FAO Plant Protection Bulletin.

Preinoculation and postinoculation root-dip treatments were tested to compare the effectiveness of insecticides and nematicides in controlling and preventing larval invasion of the nematode *M. graminicola* under upland conditions. Each chemical was used at rates of 0, 25, 50, 100, and 200 ppm.

In the postinoculation treatments, infective larvae of the nematode were first allowed to invade the roots. Dipping roots in oxamyl at 200 ppm for 12 h reduced the number of surviving endoparasites as effectively as dipping them in the same chemical at 100 ppm for 24 h. Both fensulfothion at 50 ppm for 12 or 24 h and phorate for 24 h were as effective as oxamyl at 100 ppm for 24 h.

In the preinoculation root dip, oxamyl and fensulfothion were more effective at 100 and 200 ppm and superior to phorate or DBCP. Postinoculation root-dip treatments with oxamyl or fensulfothion for 24 h were as effective as preinoculation treatments for 12 h. The order of effectiveness of the chemicals was oxamyl or fensulfothion > phorate > DBCP. Fensulfothion and oxamyl retained toxicity for 15 days after root dipping; phorate, for 10 days; and DBCP, for 5 days. Systemic chemicals such as oxamyl, phorate, or fensulfothion persisted longer in plants when used as root dip.

A surveillance chart for recording decisions on pest management. University of Hawaii, Honolulu, Hawaii, USA.

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